

MUSIC AS A COMPLIMENTARY THERAPY DURING PREGNANCY

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ABSTRACT

Music therapy used as Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM) now a days. Pregnancy is a condition in which mother have to face various psychological and mood changes activates, but gynecologist always trying to handle them without using a drug, because drug in form of chemical can affect growth and development of fetus. Many congenital disorders are the result of the use of various types of drugs use in pregnancy. To avoid such conditions gynecologists are always trying to minimize the use of drugs during pregnancy. The present study is aimed to use the music for emotional regulation, relaxation and pain management, help in parturition, anxiety, stress and facilitate the child's growth and development. Present study prove that music can used as complimentary therapy, if used scientifically. The purpose of this study was to examine that why we feel cool and calm when we listen specific music. How the music therapies affect us? Is pleasant sound have the power to effect the gynecological condition.

Keywords : Pregnancy, Music therapy, Heartbeat, Fetal development, Parturition.

Introduction

Shakespeare once wrote: "If music be the food of love, play on." Profound words, true, but the Bard failed to mention that music is not just nourishment for the heart, but also for the soul. Today we are living in the sea of chemicals.

We are using them in most of our activity for making our life easy.

They can do this but on the other side they are also responsible for creating various type of disease or disorder to cure them we are again using chemicals in form of drug. There is no debut that drugs have the ability to cure them, but on the other side it is a well establish fact that each drug have some short of side effects on the body of livings including human body and sometime side effects are converting in to serious problems leading up to death.

Children's are most valuable gift of nature. A woman face various physiological and psychological

problems during pregnancy and child birth. It is a peaceful moment when mother listen and feel fetus heartbeat. Most people use word like to galloping to describe how the heart rate sound. The truth is that a normal fetal heart rate changes during the stage of pregnancy.

In normal way at about five-seven week's gestation baby's heart begin to beat and it can be hear by vaginal ultrasound.

In present study ultrasounds are conducted at nine week of pregnancy but the impact of music on fetus observed after eighteen week of pregnancy because at this age hearing sense developed well. At this point a normal fetal heart rate is about the same as the mother's' 80 to 85 bpm.

From this point, it will increased its rate about three beats per minute per day during the first month of pregnancy. Many other factors can affect heart rate of an unborn offspring such as music. Fetus also experiences

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sound from the mother's body outside the womb which impact the development. Scientist agree that in the parental period the fetus is capable of learning, listening. Fetus capable to blinking eye during advanced pregnancy, several reactions depend on the type and rhythm of music.

Such as pop hip hop music increased the heart rate of fetus while romantic songs increased fetal movement. Music therapy is defined as the controlled use of music, music can heal physiological and psychological & emotional stress of individual during the treatment of an illness or disability.

Pain, Mood swings are a normal experience during **pregnancy**. Mother body is going through physical and hormonal changes affecting their day-to-day life. Mother having **emotional** ups and downs. While **mood swings** are common, depression is a different matter.

There is also a difference between feeling nervous and having anxiety that interferes with mother ability to get through the day. Depression and anxiety aren't the same as "mood swings." Depression or anxiety during pregnancy can increase the risk of experiencing postpartum depression or anxiety. Both depression and anxiety can have adverse health effects on mother and fetus.

Music work as a therapy it's brings variety of experiences such as promoting muscular relaxation, relieving anxiety and depression in mother, even fetus also realized and enjoy music therapy, during therapy fetus movement and heartbeat changes. So music can be used to decrease pain or stress during pregnancy and help growth and development of fetus.

Findings of present work are so surprising. This article intends to contribute to a scientific basis of this promising movement and suggests a multidimensional framework for the use of music therapy in controlling pregnancy mood swing of mother and heartbeat, movement of fetus.

Material and Methods

- Volunteers are selected form Mohan Swaroop Hospital, Dadari, GB Nagar. The procedure is

explained to volunteers and they signed their consent form prior to perform the study.

- During study music is provided through two head phone (Wireless headphones having frequency adjusters, sounds meter and Android phone). One head phone was paced on abdomen/womb of mother and another on the ear of mother as shown in photograph (6,7). To control the sound frequency, pitch a third headphone is used by instructor. All the three headphones working thorough a single point
- Selected sounds are given to volunteers through headphone and heartbeat, movements are observed through USG machine and ECG of fetus.
- Toshiba (Model Nemio XG) having antenatal facility (scan movement and position of fetus and E.C.G electro cardiograph of fetus) used for the study.
- The study was conducted on twenty eight subjects (volunteer) with pre and post music therapy treatment and repeated twice with every volunteers.
- Music used during study are selected on the basis of DCS theory of neuroendocrine stimulation (Developed by one of the author in 2010). All the volunteers have to fill a questioner for the selection of the music. Hip-hop, religious, romantic, folk of high and low frequency songs are selected on the basis of questioner filled by subject.
- All twenty eight subjects (volunteer) give their consent to perform the study so they are selected. Fifty nine ultrasounds are conducted on these subject during the course of study.

Result

In most of the cases heartbeat and movement of fetus increased significantly by music therapy. Variation of heart beat depend on different types of ragas such as pop hip hop music best choice of fetus, music therapy increased heart rate of fetus 5 to 27 BPM it's depend on the nature of fetus. 8 to 9 week fetus also realized the rhythm of music

Table-1: Showing all observation of volunteers involved in the study

Sr No.	Volunteer Number	Sound Frequency (in decibel)	Age of mother	Pregnancy in Week	Heart Beat without Music Therapy –A (in beat/minute)	Heart Beat with Music Therapy –B (in beat/minute)	Difference in Heart beat	Movement	Movement of fetus	Mother reaction during therapy
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	16.	49-60 db	26	9.1			0	↑	No change	Feel relaxed
2	16.	49-65 db	26	9.1			0	↑↑↑	No change	Feel relaxed
3	14.	48-50 db	19	9.3			0	↑↑	No change	Feel relaxed
4	14.	35-38 db	19	9.3			0	↑↑↑	No change	Feel relaxed
5	20.	46-55 db	21	9.5			0	↑	No change	No change
6	20.	48-59 db	21	9.5			0		No change	No change
7	25.	56-59 db	26	11.5			0	↑	Increased Movement	Feeling happy and relax
8	25.	51-65 db	26	11.5			0	↑↑	No change	Feeling happy and relax
9	21.	47-55 db	24	13.6			0	↑	No change	Feel relaxed
10	21.	47-60 db	24	13.6			0	↑↑↑	No change	Feel relaxed
11	7.	55-60 db	23	14	150	156	6	↑↑↑	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed
12	7.	42-49 db	23	14	150	153	3	↑↑	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed
13	15.	42-53 db	29	15.4	144	144	0	↑	No change	Feel relaxed
14	15.	48-60 db	29	15.4	163	163	0	↑↑↑	No change	Feel relaxed
15	22.	51-68 db	24	15.4	135	148	13	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
16	22.	49-60 db	24	15.4	139	144	5	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
17	19.	48-55 db	25	17.6	147	132	-15	↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
18	19.	48-60 db	25	17.6	147	132	-15	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
19	10.	49-60 db	22	20	139	144	5	↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
20	10.	48-50 db	22	20	139	144	5	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
21	13.	49-65 db	25	20	144	147	3	↑↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
22	13.	49-56 db	25	20	144	153	9	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
23	1.	46-50 db	20	23	139	132	-7	↓	No change	Feel good and relaxed
24	1.	55-59 db	20	23	139	132	-7	↑	No change	Feel good and relaxed
25	26.	49-62 db	24	25.3	136	139	3	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel good Movement of fetus increased
26	26.	49-51 db	24	25.3	136	144	8	↓	No change	Feel good Movement of fetus increased
27	6.	49-60 db	24	27	129	144	15	↑↑	No change	Feeling relaxed
28	6.	37-48 db	24	27	129	142	13	↑↑	No change	Feeling relaxed
29	9.	48-60 db	22	27	139	147	8	↑	No change	No change
30	9.	49-52 db	22	27	139	132	-7	↑↑↑	No change	No change
31	4.	30-45 db	26	29	139	136	-3	↓	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed
32	4.	37-48 db	26	29	139	136	-3	↑↑	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed

33	4.	49-60 db	26	29	139	144	5	↑↑	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed
34	11.	48-52 db	19	31	134	136	2	↓	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
35	11.	39-53 db	19	31	134	136	2	↑↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
36	12.	45-58 db	21	31	134	139	5	↑↑	No change	Feel good
37	12.	46-50 db	21	31	134	132	-2	↓	No change	Feel good
38	28.	49-52 db	28	32.1	139	142	3	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feeling relax
39	28.	48-56 db	28	32.1	139	147	8	↓	Increased Movement	Feeling relax
40	24.	52-60 db	20	32.3	136	150	14	↑	Increased Movement	Feel good Movement of fetus increased
41	24.	50-55 db	20	32.3	136	144	8	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel good Movement of fetus increased
42	5.	32-45 db	35	33	142	142	0	↑	No change	No change
43	5.	57-60 db	35	33	142	156	14	↓↓	No change	No change
44	8.	49-63 db	21	33	139	147	8	↑↑	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed
45	8.	50-52 db	21	33	139	144	5	↑	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed
46	27.	50-55 db	26	33.3	144	132	-12	↑↑↑	Increased Movement	Feeling happy and stress free
47	27.	50-54 db	26	33.3	144	132	-12	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feeling happy and stress free
48	23.	51-61 db	30	33.4	125	142	17	↑↑	No change	Feeling nervous
49	23.	49-60 db	30	33.4	125	129	4	↓↓	No change	Feeling nervous
50	23.	52-60 db	30	33.4	125	129	4	↑	Increased Movement	Feeling nervous
51	23.	50-60 db	30	33.4	125	136	11	↑↑↑	Increased Movement	Feeling nervous
52	3.	49-60 db	23	34	136	134	-2	↑↑	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed
53	3.	42-49 db	23	34	136	129	-7	↑	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed
54	18.	49-63 db	24	34.4	134	129	-5	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
55	18.	46-50 db	24	34.4	134	142	8	↑↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
56	17.	49-62 db	23	34.6	142	144	2	↑↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
57	17.	49-62 db	23	34.6	142	147	5	↑↑	Increased Movement	Feel relaxed
58	2.	46-51 db	20	36	129	153	24	↑↑	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed
59	2.	42-53 db	20	36	129	147	18	↑	Faster movement	Feel good and relaxed

Heartbeat of fetus of volunteer number 14,16, 20,21,25 not observed

Discussion

Research work was conducted on volunteer pregnant women's to measure cardiac activity of fetus through abdominal ultrasound to give music therapy (different types of ragas). The findings are significant and highly significant.

There are highly valid quality standards for antenatal, perinatal, and postnatal health care. They refer crucially to the control of physiological and mental risk factors such as hypertension in pregnancy or depressive dispositions. From this perspective, we understand music

therapy as an add-on intervention, as a way to facilitate health promotion as well as preventive measures, and to improve individual and social well-being. In carefully balanced collaboration with obstetrics and midwifery, music therapy helps to stabilize physiological and psychological conditions during pregnancy and to enhance the sustainability of antenatal care measures.

We found variation of heart beat depend on the different types of sounds such as pop, hip hop music is one of the best choice of fetus , the sound of music increase the heart rate of fetus 5-27 bpm it's depend on the

nature of fetus. 8 to 9 week's fetus also realized the rhythm of music. Fetus react according to the choice of mother (i.e) if mother enjoyed during therapy so murmured of heart beat increased. Mother age & mentality also play a key roll in the fetus activity. Some of the mothers are religious in nature so their fetus movement increased through religious music (bhajan or qawwalees). Romantic songs are the second choice of fetus, when mother hear romantic song, the heart rate of fetus have increased at few points but fetus moved faster with the rhythm of hip hop music, mostly fetus shows bicycling movement (of both feet called stepping and stepping) during therapy, which is very important in helping to turn the baby upside down for a normal delivery. So music given during pregnancy will be helpful in parturition. Even few fetus shows half cycling movement through folk dancing songs in advanced pregnancy (32 weeks or more till delivery). 8 to 9 week fetus also starting rolling movement during therapy. When antenatal mother and fetus both treated with romantic music, the movement of fetus slow down according to romantic music but the murmured of heart increased magnificently.

The vigorous movement of fetus may have painful in some women's but maximum women's admitted in survey that during music therapy pain of vigorous movement of fetus measurably decreased and they feel relaxed during and after therapy. Mostly women admitted that Classical dancing songs play a major role to decrease

pain of vigorous half cyclic or rolling movement of fetus. Pain in lower abdomen is a major problem of mostly women's, which is decreased by music therapy in many cases during and after therapy.

Significant findings

Fetus moved faster during hip-hop and romantic songs which reflects that fetus enjoying it. Increased blood pressure and fast breath of fetus show during hip hop music (DJ remix songs). Slow paced music leads to lower heart rate comparison to their baseline values. The soft sound of romantic songs with low rhythm are perfect for fetus or infants. The increase in bicycling movement observed during hip-hop and stepping movement increased in romantic songs. Music positively impact the health of adults or infants but pain or stress during pregnancy have decreased few points by music therapy (i.e music decreased the level of stress during pregnancy), which results to control the pregnancy mood swing of the mother. The mother voice and reactions is one of the most important sensual stimuli for the fetus. Music also help to overcome delivery pain through DCS theory of neuroendocrine stimulation.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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Fig-1: ultrasonography (Pres and post music therapy) of volunteer in which movement and heartbeat increased and mother feel relaxed.

Fig-2: ultrasonography (Pres and post music therapy) of volunteer number-19 in which movement increased and heartbeat decreased, and mother feel relaxed.

Fig-2: Showing positional placemats during music therapy of volunteers

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